

USAGE OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL METHODS IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In this article it is emphasized at identifying the educational potential of creative teaching as the most effective means of communicative competence formation in the process of foreign language teaching. The study of the creativity problem has its own genesis. The nature of creativity was mentioned even in the works of ancient philosophers. As for the present, the concepts of “creativity” and “creativity” have been studied and presented in the works of foreign researchers – T.M. Amabile (1), E. De Bono (2), J.P. Guilford (3), E.P. Torrance (4), etc., and Russian scientists – T.A. Barysheva and Y.A. Zhigalov (5), D.B. Bogoyavlenskaya (6), I.A. Zimnyaya (7), E.P. Ilyin (8) and others. At first the creativity problem was the object of psychologists’ close attention.*

Keywords: *international requirements, psychological-pedagogical literature, initial level, child development, pedagogical monitoring, speech initiative.*

INTRODUCTION

The traditional foreign language teaching model, dominating in the Russian professional education system, is not generally able to fundamentally solve the problem of the high quality training and competitiveness of higher school graduates. School should teach students to think and to learn – these are pedagogical imperatives of the modern era, which, in our opinion, is in tune with creative teaching. Our research is aimed Starting from the second half of the XX century the creativity problem has been the part of Russian and foreign pedagogical science researches.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the XXI century under globalization conditions the foreign language knowledge level of a higher language school graduate must meet the international requirements and standards. This level, being the basis of multicultural language personality professional competence, is aimed at providing his/ her competitiveness both on the domestic and international job markets. Our research is aimed Starting from the second half of the XX century the creativity problem has been the part of Russian and foreign pedagogical science researches. The development of creative approach to higher school teaching is represented in the works of modern Russian pedagogues and psychologists: V.I. Andreev (9), A.V. Morozov and D.V. Chernylevsky (10), and others. The main methods of our research are theoretical ones (the systematic analysis of psychological-pedagogical, scientific-methodical literature on the research problem) and methods of empirical level (the method of the survey, questionnaires, pedagogical monitoring, experiment).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The main goal of the experiment was in identifying the level of student communicative competence formation while teaching speaking in the creative educational process. During the experiment, the following tasks were solved: 1) to determine the initial level of students’ communicative competence development; 2) to identify the level of its development formation,

dynamics and tendencies on the intermediate and final stages of the experiment; 3) to use students' communicative competence level self-assessment results for its further development in the process of experiment on the basis of the portfolio; 4) to reveal experimentally the communicative competence development efficiency in the creative teaching conditions. The experimental work was held at the Department of French Philology of Kazan Federal University. The senior students (of the 3d – 5th years) of the Department divided into two, control and experimental, groups were involved into the experiment. To determine the dynamics of student development and communicative competence formation the testing of student knowledge and skills was held three times. Moreover, in our experiment we conducted pedagogical monitoring on the basis of the European language portfolio, the so-called portfolio technology (11). The monitoring was aimed at the analysis and self-assessment of students' achievements and more accurate planning of their further educational activity on a foreign language acquisition in the creative teaching process. The creative teaching, in our opinion, is the organization of such creative work, as a result of which it becomes possible for the subjects of educational activity to form new creative products distinguished by novelty, original solution, i.e. the work that is capable to satisfy the needs of a person in self-education, self-development and creative self-expression. “The main task of creative teaching is creative potential opening and personality transformation in an active and creative person, as for being applied to the study at the University it is the student's acquisition of his/ her own individuality. For this purpose it is necessary to teach students to think independently, to have his/ her own point of view, to be able to justify and defend it in the discussion, to make non-standard decisions, to demonstrate the ability and willingness to apply creative qualities in practice” (12, p. 152). In language education the main purpose of foreign language teaching at the University is the formation of language personality communicative competence. It is about “knowledge, skills and qualities of language personality that allow this personality to be efficient in speech and thought” (13, p. 142). The socio-cultural component of communicative competence is of special importance, and it involves students' mastering the national-cultural specificity of the target language country and the ability to build their verbal and nonverbal behavior according to this specificity, and also implies “...successful learning of facts of 2 and more ethnic cultures...” (14, p. 2136). “Communicative competence”, in our opinion, can be represented as an integrative property of the personality, his/ her ability to understand and produce foreign-language statements in various socially determined situations, taking into account the language and social rules that are observed by native speakers and as a set of skills that according to the purpose, means and methods are adequate to different communication tasks. Characterizing communicative competence, it should be noted that it has an internal structure and includes a number of interrelated components having certain relationships and forming certain integrity, unity. The main components of communicative competence are: 1) linguistic competence, 2) sociolinguistic competence, 3) sociocultural competence, 4) strategic competence, 5) discourse competence, 6) social competence. The interaction of the communicative competence main components – of the linguistic and nonlinguistic parts – is an essential requirement for the realization of the communication process itself, and of the communicative competence forming process as well in teaching foreign languages. It should be noted that the competence approach in language education is aimed at strengthening practical orientation and formation of graduates' key and professional competencies. In our opinion, the competence approach means not only a particular form of organizing educational process, but also the formation of a creative educational environment that

is of great importance. The creative environment in a broad sense means the totality of favourable conditions motivating the development of creative personality, his/ her creative potential that is realized without compulsion from the environment. Distinctive features of creative didactic environment in teaching foreign languages are sociability of the educational process, pragmatic, developing and active nature of teaching in the inter-subject integration and strengthening sociocultural component as well as culturally oriented teaching. One of the goals is “the development of thinking, memory and imagination which are capable of forming both language and sociocultural competence of students” (15, p.104). Under globalization conditions in the XXI century the acquisition of intercultural competence, which is expressed in the ability to enhance the knowledge continuously, to change the behavior and © Journal of Language and Literature, ISSN: 2078-0303, Vol. 5. No. 3.2014 78 | www.ijar.lit.az/philology.php attitude to other cultures so that to show flexibility and open-mindedness in the dialogue with native speakers of other linguo-societies, is of great importance (16). Mastering a foreign language as a means of intercultural communication is impossible without knowledge of the socio-cultural and sociolinguistic characteristics of the target language country. Thus, in this context, it is important to use authentic materials (original publicistic and literary texts, documentary and feature films, multimedia programs, Internet resources, and etc.) in educational process and during independent work; the basic criterion of material selection being its linguisticultural and cross-cultural value. Today educational Internet resources have great advantages: • the urgency, novelty and availability of materials, the possibility of their use for solving creative tasks; • variety, linguistic and cultural value of authentic materials; • audio - and visual information on the theme studied. New information and communication technologies due to their didactic properties contribute to more complete realization in practice of socio-cultural, multicultural and competency-based approaches in teaching foreign languages, and create virtual language and cultural environment. Didactic possibilities of modern information and communication technologies allow a completely new look at the organization of educational process. For example, along with the traditional book editions there is an opportunity to widely use multimedia textbooks with an interactive structure, as well as educational Internet resources selected by the teacher on the theme studied: hotlist, treasure hunt, subject sampler, multimedia scrapbook, and webquest. With the help of information and communication technologies the cognitive process can be directed according to students’ interests. These technologies contribute to the development of students’ self-organization and develop their creativity abilities. Creative educational technologies, including search and research, games, interactive, command forms and methods of students’ work contribute to the interpersonal interaction formation in the target language. The use of information technologies promotes not only foreign language communicative competence development in all variety of its components, but students’ information competence development as well (mastering new information technologies, understanding the range of their use, and a critical attitude to information distributed). Giving more freedom for students’ creativity activates their interests and increases their language learning motivation. Thus, shifting to active teaching methods in conditions of higher education information technologies allows giving considerable time for solving creative, cognitive problems in teaching foreign languages. The introduction of information technologies changes students’ educational activity that becomes constructive, interactive, reflective and more creative. Thanks to new information Internet Web 2.0 technologies students acquire the opportunities for the development of a fundamentally new form of self-cognition and foreign

language learning (17). The formation of the student autonomy as his/ her personal characteristic is one of the principles of foreign language creative teaching. “The problem of development of cognitive independence... is due to the growing need for optimization of educational process and is still under the close attention of the didactics scientists” (18, p.1). Students’ independent and creative realization of educational activity has a positive impact on the acquisition of communicative competence and promotes sustainable habit of independent work on the language studied. The maximum approximation of the educational process to the process of real communication is most effective while using interactive and collective forms of foreign language teaching that encourage communicative activity, speech initiative, increase of the motivation, development of reflection, critical thinking, social perception. We believe that active methods of foreign language teaching are in tune with creative methods, enriching the student activities with the elements of problems, creativity and scientific search. These are non-traditional problematic lectures (lecture-research, lecture-discussion and lecture-interview), role-playing games, theatre-situational creative classes, discussions, heuristic discussions, project method, etc. From the perspective of didactics the active methods are correlated with the communicative approach, aimed at establishing students’ foreign language communicative competence that is required for intercultural communication. So, creative organization of educational process mobilizes and motivates students. It should be noted that the methods of creative teaching have a significant impact on the level of student interests in foreign language learning and their motivation that the quality of education depends on (© Journal of Language and Literature, ISSN: 2078-0303, Vol. 5. No. 3. 2014 B a k u , A z e r b a i j a n | 79). We questioned the senior students to determine priorities in the motivational aspect of the study. The main reasons for foreign language learning are the following: 1) to acquire profession – 82%; 2) access to foreign-language information – 77%; 3) career promotion – 75%; 4) to meet the needs of self-realization – 47%. The successful realization of creative teaching depends on the personality of a foreign language teacher, who should have a high level of professional skills, creative thinking, creative potential, methods and technologies for the development of students’ creative abilities, sensitivity to pedagogical innovations. During the experiment, the development of student communicative competence was provided with teaching speaking as one of the productive kinds of speech activity in the process of teaching foreign languages. The dominant organizing form of creative teaching was practical classes, where the study of vital issues of modern French society was focused on. For example: “The problems of the youth”, “The position of foreigners and immigration problems”, “Leisure time and activities of the French”, “The metropolis problems”, and etc. The creative teaching was formed on three levels of speech independence development: copying, reproductive-creative and constructive-creative. Constructive-creative level of informative-speech-independence implies the ability to creatively use the developed speech skills and on the basis of their improvement to fulfill the difficult transfer to a new speech problem solution. All types and forms of teaching were focused on the development of student foreign language communicative competence and creative abilities, their imagination and creative thinking, in accordance with the personality-oriented approach based on subject-subject relations. The experimental part of our research included three stages: establishing, forming and final. At the beginning of the experiment the first testing of the students’ knowledge and skills was carried out to determine the initial level of communicative competence. In general, the results on the establishing stage of the experiment in the control and

experimental groups did not differ significantly and were not high at all, reflecting the average level of communicative competence.

Pedagogical principle can perhaps appear a challenging, even difficult word. Some thirty years ago, the educational historian Brian Simon wrote a critique of educational practice in England under the title 'Why no pedagogy in England?' (Simon, 1981). He described pedagogy as the 'science of teaching' and argued that 'no such science exists in England'. He contrasted 'the educational tradition of the Continent, [where] the term "pedagogy" has an honoured place... The concept of teaching as a science has strong roots in this tradition' (Simon, 1981:77). In England, by contrast, Simon argued that thinking about teaching and learning was highly eclectic, confusing aims and methods, and with no clear philosophical or conceptual underpinning for what was done in the classroom. An enormous amount has changed in classrooms since 1981, and a great deal more attention has focused on the way teachers teach in national policy and research. In the later 1990s, the government established the national literacy and national numeracy projects, which set out firm guidance on teaching primary literacy and numeracy based on research into best practice. The projects were subsequently taken up and expanded as the national literacy and numeracy strategies in 1997, which defined a clear national approach to teaching in primary schools. In the first years of the 21st century, the principles of the primary strategies formed the basis for the secondary national strategy, extending the national program of best-practice informed professional development to secondary schools (DfES, 2004). There was a concurrent interest in teaching and learning in research: the Teaching and Learning Research Program (TLRP, 2003) was the most extensive program of educational research ever undertaken in the United Kingdom, with a series of research and dissemination projects designed to explore, research and develop teaching and learning in schools. Nonetheless, in 2004, Robin Alexander argued that there was 'still no pedagogy in England' (Alexander, 2004:19). Defining pedagogy as 'both the act of teaching and its attendant discourse', framed by 'ideas, values and evidence' (ibid), Alexander argued that national policy remained ignorant about the theoretical underpinnings of pedagogy, and was underinformed on 'evidence and debate about children, learning, teaching, curriculum and culture' (ibid:26). Grimmit, who defines pedagogy as 'a theory of teaching and learning encompassing aims, curriculum content and methodology' makes a similar point about the introduction of the national curriculum: It would have been wholly feasible for the government to have introduced a system of education which gave prominence to assessment while drawing upon an extensive and respectable body of educational theory. Equally they could have also established a unified National Curriculum grounded in well-established theories of teaching and learning. Instead, they chose to prescribe a framework of content and outcomes for the National Curriculum which was... free of curriculum theory and made no attempt to address the characteristics of the learner or identify what the underlying principles of education should be. Grimmit, 2000:16, For Alexander, drawing on international education practices, pedagogy has two meanings: 'the act of teaching' and a wider conceptual meaning – 'ideas, values and evidence' about 'children, learning, teaching, curriculum and culture' (Alexander, 2004:7–8). In continental Europe, 'pedagogy' is a term that refers to more than the practice and techniques of teaching in the classroom; it refers also to the theories – of children, of learning – that underpin practices. In the words of James and Pollard: 'pedagogy' expresses the contingent relationship between teaching and learning... and does not treat teaching as something that can be considered separately from an understanding of how learners learn' (James & Pollard, 2011:280). 6 © National College for School Leadership In a study drawn from

practice in history classrooms, Husbands (2010) argues that the knowledge-base for effective practice comprises the interaction of subject-matter knowledge, knowledge about pedagogic approaches and knowledge about children and their development. Similarly, Siraj-Blatchford (2008), commenting on the training of early years teachers, argues for the interactions of good subject knowledge, good knowledge of play-based approaches and free play, understanding of the pedagogy of subject-specific education and the hierarchy of conceptual development, and understanding of child development so that subject learning is approached constructively.

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